

TERRIFIC
BIOBASED FLAGSHIP PACKAGING SOLUTIONS

Next generation circular biobased flagship packaging: a catalyst for the green transition

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CBE JU	Circular Biobased Europe Joint Undertaking
BIC	Biobased Industries Consortium

Disclaimer

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Next generation circular bio-based flagship packaging: a catalyst for the green transition

BIOPLASTICS IN INDUSTRIAL PACKAGING: AN ALTERNATIVE FOR A MORE SUSTAINABLE SECTOR

Bioplastics have been present in the plastics sector since its inception. There are different types, such as bio-based plastics (produced from these sources), biodegradable plastics (microorganisms available in the environment convert the materials into natural substances such as water, carbon dioxide and compost), or plastics that have both properties. However, it was not until the 1990s, when the modern bioplastics industry as such developed, that their application became widespread. In this regard, consumption has grown considerably in recent years, reaching a production capacity of 2.02 million tonnes in 2023, and is expected to reach 5.73 million tonnes in 2029¹.

In contrast to this trend, there is a certain reluctance on the part of users and even packaging producers, who consider that these materials are not capable of fulfilling the functionality required for certain applications, such as products that need a high barrier. On the other hand, there is European legislation, in which the presence of bioplastics is still very limited. An example of this is the Directive 2019/904² on the reduction of the impact of certain plastic products on the environment, also known as SUPD (Single Use Plastics Directive), which only considers the use of unmodified natural bio-based materials, thus excluding materials such as the aforementioned PLA or PHA. Another more recent case is Directive 2025/40 on packaging and packaging waste or PPWR (Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation)³, which only promotes the use of compostable materials in very specific applications, such as those containing an organic product inside, like tea bags or coffee capsules, or labels for vegetables/fruits. Nevertheless, harmonised standards establishing technical specifications and requirements for compostable materials are expected to be developed by February 2026, promoting their use in a much wider range of applications than is currently defined.

With the aim of demonstrating the functionality of these materials and their benefits as potentially more sustainable alternatives to current fossil-based materials, a large number of research projects are being carried out. ITENE leads or collaborates in numerous projects in this area, such as the SEALIVE project, coordinated by ITENE, and TERRIFIC, coordinated by Novamont.

SEALIVE, advanced biopolymers to mitigate contamination in soil and marine ecosystems.

The transition towards a truly circular economy in the packaging sector requires a profound change in how we design, produce, use and finally manage materials. In recent years European regulatory pressure combined with growing social awareness of pollution in soils, rivers and seas, has driven the need to develop advanced and sustainable materials capable of offering technical performance comparable to conventional plastics but with a substantially lower environmental impact. In this context, ITENE has played a leading role by coordinating the European project SEALIVE dedicated to the development of bio-based materials and circular solutions for both terrestrial and marine applications.

The SEALIVE project brought together a multidisciplinary consortium of more than twenty organizations committed to the transition towards next-generation bioplastics. Under ITENE's coordination, the project developed various formulations based on PLA, PHAs, starch and innovative blends derived from renewable biomass sources, such as microalgae. The key to achieving advanced properties (including mechanical, thermal, processability and even controlled degradation ratio depending on the application) was both the development of tailor-made formulations using innovative additives and the implementation of new bio-based fluorescent markers which allow these materials to be identified in sorting facilities, facilitating their recyclability and traceability within waste management systems.

One of SEALIVE's greatest contributions has been the validation of these new developments under industry-representative conditions. Throughout the project, eight different final demonstrators were produced, ranging from compostable food packaging (suitable for home or industrial composting, depending on the application) and flexible films for freezing applications to agricultural mulch films, among others. In addition, products with high environmental impact potential were also developed, including reusable and recyclable cutlery, reusable and traceable fishing crates (via RFID technology) and biodegradable fishing nets for marine environments. These prototypes were designed not only to meet technical requirements but also to minimize the generations of pollutants in soil and sea when inevitably some of them escape conventional collection systems.

Beyond the technical advances in developing these new sustainable materials, SEALIVE also focused on life cycle assessment, the definition of sustainable business models and alignment with the European regulatory framework. The consortium evaluated possible gaps in existing European standards for bio-based and biodegradable materials, proposing new lines of work for their optimization. At the same time, recommendations were proposed for European institutions to support the coherent integration of bioplastics into waste management, decarbonization and circular economy policies. This holistic approach has ensured not only the technical viability of the developed materials but also their environmental, regulatory and socioeconomic relevance.

TERRIFIC, from biorefinery to the industrialisation of high-barrier bio-based packaging.

TERRIFIC is a Flagship project supported by the Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking and its members, funded by the European Union under grant agreement number 101157635. TERRIFIC aims to reform the packaging sector with bio-based solutions that enhance performance, circularity and

resource efficiency throughout the value chain, boosting the development of a bioeconomy model able to decouple the European development from the use of resources. TERRIFIC flagship biobased products showcase the potential of bioeconomy to drive ecological transition, circularity, and to reach important goals in pollution prevention and decarbonization.

TERRIFIC will demonstrate a first-of-its-kind multipurpose biorefinery to produce bio-based materials starting from sustainable, EU-sourced feedstocks, and will implement a platform of novel biomaterials responding to packaging sector needs in terms of thermal and barrier properties, while meeting technical and durability requirements. Eight flagship packaging products will be developed and validated across the entire value chain, considering different end-of-life scenarios and proposing secondary value chains based on recycled biopolymer materials for non-food packaging solutions.

Figure 1. General scheme of the project TERRIFIC.

The eight bio-based packaging products to be developed at TERRIFIC will contain more than 95% renewable sources and will provide real packaging solutions following three technological trajectories: a) paper/pulp packaging laminated with bio-based films, b) rigid thermoplastic materials and c) flexible thermoplastic materials.

The first line of development will produce high-barrier packaging laminated with paper in stick pack format for dietary supplements, pulp-based trays laminated with an easy-open bio-based barrier film for fresh products, and flexible multilayer films suitable for crispy snacks. In terms of rigid packaging, thermoformed packaging with barrier and thermal resistance will be produced for yoghurt and dairy products, injected capsules with high barrier and sufficient resistance for coffee, and low-density foamed thermal boxes with improved thermal resistance for frozen products. Finally, with regard to materials for flexible applications, bio-based tea bags with improved performance in contact with hot

water have been proposed, as well as bubble wrap for packaging applications with greater air retention capacity, increasing its shelf life.

ITENE's involvement in TERRIFIC focuses on the development of thermoformed packaging for yoghurt and dairy products, which is intended not only to have improved barrier properties, increasing the shelf life of the product, but also to allow the end of life of the packaging to be approached from different angles in order to optimise its circularity. In this regard, different end-of-life, including both mechanical recycling and home composting, will be evaluated, with the aim, in any case, of reducing the carbon footprint up to 55% for selected materials, without releasing microplastics into the environment.

To this end, starting with materials produced by Novamont with more than 95% bio-based content, ITENE carries out a two-stage transformation process, processing of sheets by cast extrusion and subsequent thermoforming, to obtain yoghurt-type packaging. The first tests carried out with the bio-based material, evaluating two different thicknesses (Figure 2), have shown very promising results in terms of both processability and packaging properties, compared to the benchmark material.

Figure 2. Thermoformed containers with reference material (left) and bio-based material from TERRIFIC (right) of medium thickness (top) and higher thickness (bottom).

On the one hand, the mechanical properties have been determined based on the compressive strength of the packaging, which has been tripled in thermoformed packaging made from the thickest sheet evaluated in comparison with the reference material. On the other hand, the oxygen barrier has been increased to more than double that of the starting material, demonstrating the great potential of the materials developed for both the proposed applications and additional applications requiring a high barrier.

It is expected that, at the end of the project, the implementation of the multipurpose biorefinery will enable the production of materials with more than 95% bio-based content, validated for different end of life scenarios, improving the circularity and resource efficiency in the products developed. With the aim of demonstrating the replicability of the TERRIFIC concept, a Multi-actor Interest Group (MIG) is being created, whose objective is to create an interactive innovation model in which key stakeholders representing all actors in the value chain are involved and new business opportunities can be exploited. This opportunity is open to different actors throughout the value chain, such as feedstock suppliers, technology providers, packaging producers and end users, brand owners, waste management operators, scientific institutions, bioplastics and packaging associations, civil society representatives, etc. who are open to evaluating the implementation of the sustainable solutions developed in TERRIFIC in their sector.

The pathway toward truly sustainable packaging requires a comprehensive approach that covers the entire value chain: from the selection of raw materials to the design of products intended for reuse, recyclability or compostability, as well as business models that ensure their industrial viability and market acceptance. Thanks to projects with positive impact such as SEALIVE and TERRIFIC, ITENE strengthens its position as a European leader in the research, development, validation and scaling up of advanced biopolymers, contributing decisively to reducing pollution and laying the foundations for a robust, efficient and industrially implementable circular economy.

Bioplásticos en el packaging industrial: una alternativa para un sector más sostenible.

Los bioplásticos han estado presentes en el sector de los plásticos desde sus inicios. Se pueden encontrar distintos tipos, como son los plásticos de base biológica (producidos a partir de dichas fuentes), biodegradables (los microorganismos que están disponibles en el medio ambiente convierten los materiales en sustancias naturales como agua, dióxido de carbono y compost), o que presenten ambas propiedades. Sin embargo, hasta la década de los 90, en la que se desarrolla la industria de los bioplásticos modernos como tal, no se ha extendido su aplicación. En este sentido, el consumo ha ido creciendo considerablemente en los últimos años, llegando a tener una capacidad de producción de 2,02 millones de toneladas en 2023, y se espera que alcancen los 5,73 millones de toneladas en 2029¹.

En contraposición a este incremento, se detecta cierta reticencia en su uso por parte de empresas usuarias e, incluso, de productores de envase, ya que se considera que presentan una funcionalidad inferior para ciertas aplicaciones, tales como la alta barrera. Otra barrera para su implementación se puede encontrar en la legislación. Un ejemplo de ello es la Directiva 2019/904² relativa a la reducción del impacto de determinados productos de plástico en el medio ambiente, también conocida como SUPD (por sus siglas en inglés, Single Use Plastics Directive), en la que solo se considera el uso de materiales bio-basados naturales no modificados, excluyendo por tanto materiales como el ácido poliláctico (PLA) o los polihidroxialcanoatos (PHA). Otro ejemplo más reciente de estas potenciales barreras del sector es la Directiva 2025/40 sobre los envases y residuos de envases o PPWR³ (por sus siglas en inglés, Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation). En esta legislación solo se impulsa el uso de materiales compostables en aplicaciones muy concretas, como son las que contienen un producto orgánico en su interior, tipo bolsas de té o cápsulas de café, o etiquetas para productos vegetales. No obstante, se espera que para febrero de 2026 se desarrollen normas armonizadas que establezcan las especificaciones técnicas y requisitos relativos a los materiales compostables, impulsando su uso en un rango de aplicaciones mucho más amplio que el definido actualmente.

Por tanto, es necesario un mayor esfuerzo en el desarrollo de materiales que permitan demostrar la funcionalidad de estos materiales y sus beneficios como potenciales alternativas más sostenibles a los materiales de origen fósil actuales. Para cumplir este objetivo, se están realizando gran cantidad de proyectos de investigación. ITENE encabeza o colabora en numerosos proyectos en este sentido, como son el proyecto SEALIVE, coordinado por ITENE, y TERRIFIC, coordinado por Novamont.

SEALIVE, biopolímeros avanzados para mitigar la contaminación en suelos y ecosistemas marinos.

¹European Bioplastics – Nova Institute (2024). <https://www.european-bioplastics.org/bioplastics-market-development-update-2024/>

² Directive (EU) 2019/904 on the reduction of the impact of certain plastic products on the environment. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2019/904/oj>

³ Regulation (EU) 2025/40 on packaging and packaging waste. https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L_202500040&pk_campaign=todays_OJ&pk_source=EUR-Lex&pk_medium=X&pk_content=Environment&pk_keyword=Regulation

El avance hacia una economía circular real en el sector del envase exige un cambio profundo en la forma en que concebimos, producimos, utilizamos y gestionamos los materiales. En los últimos años la presión regulatoria europea, unida a la creciente sensibilidad social ante la contaminación en suelos, ríos y mares, ha impulsado la necesidad de desarrollar materiales sostenibles y avanzados capaces de ofrecer prestaciones técnicas comparables a los plásticos convencionales, pero con un impacto ambiental sustancialmente menor. En este contexto, ITENE ha desempeñado un papel protagonista liderando el proyecto europeo SEALIVE dedicado al desarrollo de materiales biobasados y soluciones circulares tanto a aplicaciones terrestres como marinas.

EL proyecto SEALIVE ha reunido a un consorcio multidisciplinar de más de veinte organizaciones comprometidas con la transición hacia bioplásticos de nueva generación. Bajo la coordinación de ITENE, en el proyecto se han desarrollado diferentes formulaciones basadas en PLA y PHAs, almidón y mezclas innovadoras a partir de fuentes de biomasa renovable (como por ejemplo microalgas). La clave para alcanzar propiedades avanzadas (mecánicas, térmicas de procesabilidad e incluso de degradación controlada, dependiendo de la aplicación) ha sido tanto el desarrollo de formulaciones a medida usando aditivos innovadores, así como el empleo de nuevos marcadores fluorescentes de base biológica que permiten identificar estos materiales en las plantas de clasificación, facilitando así su reciclabilidad y trazabilidad dentro de los sistemas de gestión de residuos.

Una de las mayores contribuciones del proyecto SEALIVE ha sido la validación de estos nuevos desarrollos en condiciones representativas de la industria. A lo largo del proyecto se han fabricado ocho demostradores finales diferentes que abarcan desde envases alimentarios compostables (doméstica e industrialmente, dependiendo de la aplicación), films flexibles para aplicaciones de congelación, o films de acolchado para agricultura, entre otros. Además, también se han desarrollado productos de alto impacto ambiental como cubiertos reutilizables y reciclables, cajas de pesca reutilizables y trazables (mediante tecnología RFID) y redes de pesca biodegradables en medio marino. Estos prototipos han sido diseñados no solo para cumplir con los requisitos técnicos, sino también para minimizar la generación de contaminantes en suelos y aguas cuando, inevitablemente, algunos de ellos escapan a los sistemas de recogida convencionales.

Además de los avances técnicos con el desarrollo de estos nuevos materiales avanzados y sostenibles, SEALIVE también ha puesto el foco en el análisis del ciclo de vida, la definición de modelos de negocio sostenibles y la alineación con el marco normativo europeo. El consorcio ha evaluado lagunas normativas en los estándares europeos existentes para materiales biobasados y biodegradables, proponiendo nuevas líneas de trabajo para su optimización. Paralelamente, también se han elaborado recomendaciones dirigidas a instituciones europeas para apoyar la integración coherente de bioplásticos en las políticas de gestión de residuos, descarbonización y economía circular. Esta aproximación holística ha permitido garantizar no solo la viabilidad técnica de los materiales desarrollados, sino también su pertinencia ambiental, regulatoria y socioeconómica.

TERRIFIC, de la biorefinería a la industrialización de los envases bio-basados alta barrera.

TERRIFIC, es un proyecto de elevado TRL, conocidos como *Flasghip project* y respaldado por la *Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking* y sus miembros, subvencionado por la Unión Europea en virtud del acuerdo de subvención 101157635. TERRIFIC tiene como objetivo desarrollar para el sector del embalaje soluciones bio-basadas que mejoren el rendimiento, la circularidad y la eficiencia de los recursos a lo largo de toda la cadena de valor, impulsando el desarrollo de un modelo de bioeconomía capaz de desvincular el desarrollo europeo del uso de recursos. Los productos bio-basados seleccionados en TERRIFIC muestran el potencial de la bioeconomía para impulsar la transición ecológica, la circularidad y alcanzar importantes objetivos en materia de prevención de la

contaminación y descarbonización.

TERRIFIC desarrollará una biorrefinería multipropósito única en su género para producir materiales de origen biológico a partir de materias primas sostenibles procedentes de la UE, e implementará una plataforma de biomateriales novedosos con el objetivo de cubrir las necesidades del sector del embalaje en términos de propiedades térmicas y de barrera, al tiempo que cumplan los requisitos técnicos y de durabilidad. Para cumplir con este cometido se desarrollarán ocho tipologías de envase y se validarán a lo largo de toda la cadena de valor, teniendo en cuenta diferentes escenarios de fin de vida y proponiendo cadenas de valor secundarias basadas en el reciclado de biopolímeros para soluciones de embalaje no alimentario.

Figura 1. Esquema general del proyecto TERRIFIC.

Los ocho envases bio-basados que se obtendrán en TERRIFIC tendrán un contenido mayor de 95% de fuentes renovables y aportarán soluciones de envase reales siguiendo tres trayectorias: a) envases de papel/pulpa laminados con films bio-basados, b) materiales termoplásticos rígidos y c) materiales termoplásticos flexibles.

Dentro de la primera línea de desarrollo se obtendrán envases de alta barrera laminados con papel tipo stick pack para suplementos dietéticos, bandejas basadas en pulpa laminadas con un film bio-basado barrera de fácil apertura para productos frescos y films multicapa flexibles que sean aptos para el envasado de aperitivos crujientes. En cuanto a la línea de envases rígidos, se obtendrán envases termoformados con barrera y resistencia térmica para envasado de yogures o productos lácteos, cápsulas inyectadas con elevada barrera y resistencia suficiente para el envasado de café, y cajas térmicas espumadas con baja densidad y resistencia térmica mejorada para el envasado de productos congelados. Finalmente, en relación con los materiales para aplicaciones flexibles, se han planteado bolsitas de té bio-basadas con comportamiento mejorado en contacto con agua caliente, y film de burbujas para aplicaciones de embalaje con mayor capacidad para retener el aire, aumentando su vida útil.

La participación de ITENE en TERRIFIC se centra en el desarrollo del envase termoformado para

aplicaciones de yogur o productos lácteos, el cual se pretende no sólo que tenga propiedades barrera mejoradas, aumentando la vida útil del producto, sino que también el fin de vida del envase pueda abordarse desde distintos puntos de vista para optimizar su circularidad. En este sentido, se valorarán distintos fines de vida, incluyendo tanto el reciclado mecánico como el compostaje doméstico, con un objetivo general de una reducción de hasta el 55% en la huella de carbono para algunos materiales, evitando la liberación de microplásticos al medio ambiente.

Partiendo de los materiales producidos por Novamont con más de un 95% de contenido bio-basado, ITENE está ya desarrollando un proceso de transformación en dos etapas, extrusión de lámina y posterior termoformado, obteniendo envases para contener yogur. Las primeras pruebas realizadas con el material bio-basado, partiendo de láminas de distinto espesor (Figura 2), han mostrado resultados muy prometedores tanto en la procesabilidad como en las propiedades del envase, en comparación con el material de referencia.

Figura 2. Envases termoformados con material de referencia (izquierda) y material bio-basado de TERRIFIC (derecha) de espesor medio (arriba) y espesor más alto (abajo).

La evaluación de las propiedades mecánicas de los nuevos materiales se basa en la resistencia a la compresión del envase, la cual se ha logrado triplicar en envases termoformados a partir de la lámina biobasada de mayor espesor evaluada con respecto al material de referencia. Por otra parte, se ha logrado incrementar la barrera al oxígeno más del doble frente al material de partida, mostrando el gran potencial de los materiales desarrollados tanto para las aplicaciones propuestas como para otras aplicaciones que requieran una alta barrera.

A la finalización del proyecto, se pretende obtener materiales con más de un 95% de contenido bio-basado, validados para cumplir distintos fines de vida, mejorando la circularidad y eficiencia del uso de recursos de los productos desarrollados. Con el objetivo de demostrar la replicabilidad del concepto de TERRIFIC, se está creando un “Grupo de Interés Multi-actor” o MIG (por sus siglas en inglés), para crear un modelo de innovación interactivo en que todos los actores de la cadena de valor estén involucrados y puedan explotarse nuevas oportunidades de negocio. Esta oportunidad está abierta para distintos actores a lo largo de la cadena de valor, tales como proveedores de materias primas, tecnología, productores de envases y usuarios finales, propietarios de marcas, operadores de gestión de residuos, instituciones científicas, asociaciones de bioplásticos y envases, representantes de la sociedad civil, u otros actores que estén abiertos a valorar la implementación de las soluciones sostenibles desarrolladas en TERRIFIC en su sector.

El camino hacia envases verdaderamente sostenibles exige un enfoque integral que recorra toda la cadena de valor: desde la elección de las materias primas hasta el diseño de productos concebidos para la reutilización, la reciclabilidad o la compostabilidad, pasando por modelos de negocio que

garanticen su viabilidad industrial y su aceptación en el mercado. Gracias a proyectos que generan impacto positivo como SEALIVE y TERRIFIC, ITENE refuerza su posición como referente europeo en la investigación, desarrollo, validación y escalado de biopolímeros avanzados, contribuyendo de manera decisiva a reducir la contaminación y a sentar las bases de una economía circular robusta, eficiente y aplicable a escala industrial.

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water have been proposed, as well as bubble wrap for packaging applications with greater air retention capacity, increasing its shelf life.

ITENE's involvement in TERRIFIC focuses on the development of thermoformed packaging for yoghurt and dairy products, which is intended not only to have improved barrier properties, increasing the shelf life of the product, but also to allow the end of life of the packaging to be approached from different angles in order to optimise its circularity. In this regard, different end-of-life, including both mechanical recycling and home composting, will be evaluated, with the aim, in any case, of reducing the carbon footprint up to 55% for selected materials, without releasing microplastics into the environment.

To this end, starting with materials produced by Novamont with more than 95% bio-based content, ITENE carries out a two-stage transformation process, processing of sheets by cast extrusion and subsequent thermoforming, to obtain yoghurt-type packaging. The first tests carried out with the bio-based material, evaluating two different thicknesses (Figure 2), have shown very promising results in terms of both processability and packaging properties, compared to the benchmark material.

On the one hand, the mechanical properties have been determined based on the compressive strength of the packaging, which has been tripled in thermoformed packaging made from the thickest sheet evaluated in comparison with the reference material. On the other hand, the oxygen barrier has been increased to more than double that of the starting material, demonstrating the great potential of the materials developed for both the proposed applications and additional applications requiring a high barrier.

It is expected that, at the end of the project, the implementation of the multipurpose biorefinery will enable the production of materials with more than 95% bio-based content, validated for different end of life scenarios, improving the circularity and resource efficiency in the products developed. With the aim of demonstrating the replicability of the TERRIFIC concept, a Multi-actor Interest Group (MIG) is being created, whose objective is to create an interactive innovation model in which key stakeholders representing all actors in the value chain are involved and new business opportunities can be exploited. This opportunity is open to different actors throughout the value chain, such as feedstock suppliers, technology providers, packaging producers and end users, brand owners, waste management operators, scientific institutions, bioplastics and packaging associations, civil society representatives, etc. who are open to evaluating the implementation of the sustainable solutions developed in TERRIFIC in their sector.

The pathway toward truly sustainable packaging requires a comprehensive approach that covers the entire value chain: from the selection of raw materials to the design of products intended for reuse, recyclability or compostability, as well as business models that ensure their industrial viability and market acceptance. Thanks to projects with positive impact such as SEALIVE and TERRIFIC, ITENE strengthens its position as a European leader in the research, development, validation and scaling up of advanced biopolymers, contributing decisively to reducing pollution and laying the foundations for a robust, efficient and industrially implementable circular economy.